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Newsletters

Flexible chemical looping combustion for combined heat and power production from biogenic residues with negative emission

Project number: 101147904
Project Coordinator: RISE
Project Manager: Amir Soleimani Salim
Duration: 2024 - 2028
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Topic: HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02-01

Ed. 2 - Feb. 2026

www.bioflexclcproject.eu/

WELCOME TO THE SECOND Bio-FlexCLC NEWSLETTER

Welcome!

This edition features some of the latest news and interview with our partners.

On our website www.bioflexclcproject.eu you will find more info on our project, public deliverables, videos and latest updates. Please follow us!

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Meet our partners

CHALMERS
UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

The Department of Space, Earth and Environment (SEE) at Chalmers University of Technology conducts research spanning fundamental and applied studies of physical processes in space, Earth, and engineered energy systems. Research at SEE covers areas such as space plasma physics, astrophysics, atmospheric science, geoscience, remote sensing, and energy technology, with strong emphasis on quantitative modeling, advanced experimentation, and system-level analysis. A significant part of the department's work targets sustainable energy conversion, carbon-neutral technologies, and understanding Earth—space interactions.

Tobias Mattisson is a Full Professor in Energy Technology at Chalmers University of Technology in Göteborg, Sweden, where he leads research on advanced thermochemical energy conversion processes. His work focuses particularly on chemical looping combustion, oxygen carrier materials, and related technologies for carbon capture and sustainable energy systems, with an extensive portfolio of publications and ongoing projects addressing material performance, fluidized-bed reactors, and low-carbon energy solutions.

Nasrin Nemati is a Postdoc researcher at the Department of Space, Earth, and Environment at Chalmers University of Technology. Her research is focused on thermochemical processes and the concepts for improving mass transfer and fuel conversion during Chemical Looping Combustion (CLC) of biomass. The research focus is experimental analysis to examine the potential value of the concept for current and future energy conversion technologies.

Interview with our partners

During one of the GA meetings, we had a chance to talk with Prof. Tobias Mattisson and Dr. Nasrin Nemati from Chalmers University of Technology. The video recap could be found on our project website www.bioflexclcproject.eu/.

Would you please introduce yourself?

Prof. Tobias Mattisson: I am a professor in fuel conversion at the Division of Energy and Technology at Chalmers University of Technology. And we are involved in the Bio-FlexCLC project around chemical looping. We are work package leader for work package 2, which is related to investigations in pilot units and also substantiation with different modelling tools. Basically the main overarching goal of that work package is to achieve a better understanding of the processes which occur in this mode of technology.

Dr. Nasrin Nemati: I am a post-doc researcher at Chalmers University of Technology. I work together with Tobias to deliver the tasks in collaboration with other partners related to work package 2 of the Bio-FlexCLC project.

Interview with our partners

How important for this project to collaborate with other RTOs and companies?

Prof. Tobias Mattisson: We need to do something on the climate change, and we have to do this rapidly. We have already approaches to achieve the targets - to get negative carbon emission. Yet we do not have proper incentives and polices in place for the stakeholders to take further steps. In this project, we are bridging this gap, we need to do something with no incentives.

Our goal is to have a technology which can be viable and economically feasible even without incentives. And this is due to the dual nature of technology that you can use it in different modes of operation I think to get scale up at a rapid rate. Basically you need to have industry industrial sectors involved, but you also need the fundamental understandings. So I think that it's quite necessary for the climate to have that kind of approach.

How do you feel in joining this GA meeting?

Dr. Nasrin Nemati: It's my first time to Thessaloniki. I think that it's very useful to have a general meeting to meet different partners in person and have the possibility to communicate. To know different aspects that have been considered from different perspectives, and to share knowledge and also get new ideas, I think the GA meetings are very important. And I found the lab tours (of CERTH) are very interesting. Hope to have further collaborations and communications with them as well.

Highlights & Updates

2nd - 3rd April 2025

Sven Anderson from GMAB presented at the Swedish Boiler Days 2025 in Gävle, Sweden.

7th April 2025

Nasrin Nemati from Chalmers University of Technology presented at Energy Technology Day 2025 in Gothenburg, Sweden

6th - 10th April 2025

Francisco Garcia in the 25th International Conference on Fluidized Bed Conversion in Nanjing, China

Highlights & Updates

7th - 8th May 2025
3rd GA meeting in CERTH, Thessaloniki

VIRTUAL TECH FORUM
Biofuels & Sustainability
 Driving Business & Market Adoption

Wed., 24th Sep 2025
 10:00-11:00 (CET)
 Online Teams event
<https://bit.ly/4IEoDAu>

Prof. Fausto Gallucci
 Professor in Chemical Engineering
 Eindhoven University of Technology, NL

Dr. Gaetano Anello
 Postdoc
 Eindhoven University of Technology, NL

Dr. Sennai A. Mesfun
 Researcher
 Research Institutes of Sweden (RISE)

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CUBE MEMCAT Bi-MeGaFuel Bio-FlexCLC

24th Sep 2025
Virtual Tech Forum with 2 EU projects, Bio-MeGaFuel and MemCat.
Recap video will be uploaded soon.

Sep 2025
Bio-FlexCLC formed partnership with Flexby project

flexby Project - Dissemination - Events

Flexby Partners with Bio-FlexCLC to Advance Sustainable Energy Innovation

Flexby has recently deepened its collaboration within the European research community by partnering with the EU-funded project Bio-FlexCLC, an important step in its ongoing clustering and networking strategy.

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 MeGaFu

Upcoming events of Bio-FlexCLC and partner projects

» May 2026
5th GA meeting in Chalmers
University of Technology

» 28th - 29th May 2026
Symposium "From Waste to Sustainable Fuels"
Barcelona, Spain
Organised by our partner projects

Symposium

From Waste to Sustainable Fuels
Comprehensive Sustainability Assessment & Product Standardisation in Next-Generation Biofuel Pathways: Integrating Waste-to-Fuel Innovations for Hard-to-Abate Sectors

28-29 May 2026
9:30-17:00 | 9:30-13:30 CET
Barcelona, Spain

Join us!

flexby FuelUp Bio2Fuel TEAPOTS AMBITION PYSOLO Fuels-C

Funded by the European Union UK Research and Innovation

» 31st Aug - 4th Sep 2026
International Conference on
Chemical Looping ICCL 2026,
Manchester, United Kingdom

 **International Conference
on Chemical Looping**
31 Aug - 4 Sept 2026, Manchester (UK)

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